

Quantum Free Particle, Stochastic Action and Its Link to Special Relativity

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In (1), the notion of a stochastic classical action is introduced and a probability is linked to $\exp(\text{constant} \cdot \text{action})$. The objective of (1) is not to derive quantum mechanics, but to derive stochastic dynamics based on maximum entropy in action space.

We have argued in a number of previous notes (2) that one may use the classical action to create a quantum free particle probability. This classical action, however, is not chosen a priori, but rather arises due to other considerations. We suggest that stochasticity is present in Newtonian mechanics at some time scale because dt is finite in $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ (Newton's second law) and so postulate that force delivery at some x, t is probabilistic within some dt and dx . A priori, dt and dx are not known, but if there is stochasticity, there should be a free particle probability, i.e. a probability (x, t) where x, t represent an x, t interaction point. Furthermore, the notion of dx and dt should arise naturally.

We note that the form $\exp(i \text{function}(x, t, p, E))$ may be introduced because free particles have no distributed variable (like energy in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case). $\exp(i \text{function}(x, t))$ immediately introduces periodicity, but we have argued that stochasticity can only exist within tiny, fixed dx, dt linked to $dp/dt = F$. In particular, one classical Newtonian scale this stochasticity is not seen. The periodicity should be directly in x and t space, suggesting $\exp(i A_1 t + i A_2 x)$. This expression, however, should be Lorentz invariant, and A_1 and A_2 should be constants, at least for a fixed m_0 and v . The reason that the one must have periodicity is that the dx and dt ranges of stochasticity in $dp/dt = F$ must appear naturally. At this point, one is led to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ with $-Et + px$ being a Lorentz invariant which satisfies the above criteria. This Lorentz invariant happens to be the classical action in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases, hence giving rise to action as being a stochastic variable (of (1)) because it is a function of the two stochastic variables x and t .

Alternatively, one may choose the $\exp(iA_1x + iA_2t)$ due to its conservation properties. One may then argue that A_1 and A_2 could also be conserved for x, t held constant, i.e. A_1 and A_2 could be linked to Newtonian energy and momentum in elastic collisions. This allows one to solve for the special relativistic $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

Given the idea of a conserved quantity form for a probability, one may argue that $\exp(i \text{Action})$ satisfies a maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a conserved constraint (which is again a link with (1).)

The question then becomes: Why should the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ be the classical action. One may note that x, t usually refer to trajectory values and so for a free particle, one has $x = vt$. This means that one may factor out t , i.e. $A = t(-E + pv)$, but this is automatically the form of the Lagrangian with E being the Hamiltonian. This holds relativistically and non-relativistically with the form: $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$. The remaining question is: Why should the classical action be Lorentz invariant? We consider $E(v) - p(v)v = -L$ such that $dE/dv - v dp/dv - p = -dL/dv \text{ partial}$. This means that $dE/dv - v dp/dv = 0$ ((1)). A Lorentz transformation, however, changes m_0 in a rest frame into $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. One may see that this solution may be obtained from ((1)) showing a direct link between the classical action approach and special relativity. The connection may be carried further as $Lt = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant, but

also the classical action (in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases). We argue that the use of the action in (1) as a stochastic variable is directly related to special relativity.

In summary, from finite dt in $dp/dt=F$, t and x are stochastic variables within some naturally appearing dx and dt . One may write a linear combination of x and t and to create a stochastic Lorent invariant variable which should appear in $\exp(i \text{ Lorentz invariant})$ and create the dx and dt units. It may then be shown that this Lorentz invariant in E,p,x,t should be equivalent to the classical action.

Stochastic x and t

We argue that the initial idea linked with stochastic dynamics and free particle quantum mechanics is the notion of a stochastic x and t . We argue that this follows from Newton's second law:

$$dp/dt = F \quad ((2))$$

because dt is finite and on a certain scale it will contain a set of t values and any one may be mapped to the action of the force. In fact, one might expect a uniform distribution within this dt . dt is small and finite, but at this point one does not know its value. Similar arguments should apply to dx . This suggests that there should exist a probability in x,t . One may ask if there are any general features of such a probability? We argue that:

$$((3)) \quad p(x_1,t_1)p(x_2,t_2) = p(x_1+x_2, t_1+t_2)$$

$$((4)) \quad dt \text{ and } dx \text{ naturally appear in } p(x,t)$$

$$((5)) \quad p(x,t) \text{ cannot have a real weight because no variable is being distributed}$$

It seems that ((5)) dictates the form:

$$\exp(i f(x,t)) \quad ((6))$$

For ((3)) and ((4)) to hold, one should have a linear expression in x,t i.e.

$$\exp(i A_1 x + i A_2 t) \quad ((7))$$

Then, $dt = \text{constant}/A_2$ and $dx = \text{constant}/A_1$.

The fact that one has a periodic situation means that one may add $\exp(i \text{ number})$ and $\exp(i \text{ number} + 3.14) = -1 \exp(i \text{ number})$. Thus, in an OR situation, the sum of these special probabilities may add to 0. This should hold in any Lorentz frame and so $A_1 x + A_2 t$ should be a Lorentz invariant. This suggests:

$$-Et + px \quad ((8))$$

Even if one did not know anything about special relativity, but only Newtonian mechanics, one could suggest the form $\exp(i(Et+px))$ solely on the basis of conservation. In particular, kinetic energy is conserved in an elastic collision and momentum always.

One could then consider that x is a vector and t a number and the mocc is a number in the rest frame and that it should change to E and $p(\text{vector})$ in the moving frame. This E is not $.5m_0v^2$ anymore, but should be linked to it. If one argues that ((8)) is a Lorentz invariant (even without knowing that there is a -1 factor for E), one would use:

$$X' = g(v) v t \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v)t \quad p' = g(v) v m_0 c c \quad \text{and} \quad E' = g(v) m_0 c c \quad ((9))$$

One then sees that a minus sign is needed in ((8)) and that

$$-g(v)g(v) t t + g(v)g(v) v v t t = - m_0 c c m_0 c c t t \quad \text{or} \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((10))$$

A probability which conserves both E, p, x, t and is hence linear in these terms may be used to derive special relativity. We note that if one only uses the idea of a probability which conserves t and x , then one could have two choices:

$$-Ex+pt \quad \text{and} \quad -Et+px \quad ((11))$$

We have considered the latter above. Considering the former, one has:

$$-Ex+pt = m_0 c c * (x=0) + (p=0) * t = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad -gm_0 c c v t + m_0 c c v g t = 0 \quad ((12))$$

((12)) allows for any value $g(v)$ which cannot be. One needs a specific $g(v)$.

Thus, one chooses

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((13))$$

As the probability which demonstrates stochasticity in x, t such that there is a natural dx and dt and Lorentz invariance. At this point, the classical action has not been mentioned. Why should ((13)) be linked to the classical action?

Classical Action

In (1), a theory of stochastic dynamics is developed by considering a priori the classical action as being stochastic. The classical action for a free particle is:

$$-m_0 \int dt \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad (\text{relativistic}) \quad .5m_0 v^2 t \quad (\text{nonrelativistic}) \quad ((14))$$

Why should this expression $\text{Action} = \text{Lagrangian} * t$ ((15)) be of interest?

Formally, one may see how Lagrangian theory is directly linked to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ if one uses $v=x/t$.

$$\text{Hamiltonian} = E = pv - L \quad \text{and} \quad p = dL/dv \text{ partial} \quad ((16))$$

Then: $-Et+px = Lt$ and so Lt must be a Lorentz invariant. ((17))

Even if one did not know about special relativity, $-Et+px$ is linear in E, p, t, x and so linked with conservation of all of these variables. This conservation must hold in any other frame so $-Et+px = -E't'+p'x'$. One may argue that $Ex-pt$ is also linear, but as we have shown linking this to mocc at $x=0$ at t yields $Ex=pt=0$ for any $g(v)$ used in a transformation and so one does not obtain a unique $g(v)$ factor.

The question remains: Why should Lagrangian theory be linked with special relativity? We consider:

$$dE(v)/dv = -p + v dp/dv - dL/dv \text{ partial} \quad \text{with} \quad p = dL/dv \text{ partial} \quad ((18))$$

Then: $dE(v)/dv = v dp/dv$ ((19))

$$\text{Using ((9))} \quad d g/dv = v d/dv (gv) \rightarrow d/dv \ln(g) = d/dv \{ .5 \ln(1-vv) \} \text{ or } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((20))$$

One may obtain the $g(v)$ of special relativity from the Lagrangian theory showing the close link.

Association with Shannon's Entropy

It is known from Maxwell-Boltzmann theory that if one has a stochastic variable e which is conserved, then for an elastic situation:

$$e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \rightarrow p(e) = C \exp(-e/T) \quad ((20))$$

Mathematically, this is equivalent to maximizing $- \sum p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to a constraint on the stochastic conserved quantity $\sum e_i p(e_i)$.

The mathematics for the stochastic $-Et+px$ with E, p fixed should be the same because E and p are conserved and so the entire action is a conserved stochastic quantity. One may have a Lagrange multiplier which is purely imaginary. Thus:

Maximizing $\sum p(-Et+px) \ln(p(-Et+px))$ subject to a constraint on the stochastic conserved variable $-Et+px$ with Lagrange multiplier $-i$ yields

$$p(e_i) = \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((21))$$

We argue that maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a conserved quantity constraint yields a probability which conserves this quantity when a product of probabilities is formed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that x and t are stochastic variables at a certain length and time scale and that this may already be seen in Newton's second law $dp/dt = F$. In particular, dt is a finite number at some time scale and does not become 0. One should then have F strike at some t and x within dt and dx with some probability. The question is then: What is dt and dx ? These should appear naturally in a probability function. This probability should then be linear in x and t for two reasons. One should have conservation of x , t , i.e. $p(x_1, t_1)p(x_2, t_2) = p(x_1 + x_2, t_1 + t_2)$ and should have a linear x and t to show the dt and dx if the probability is of the form $\exp(i A_1 x + i A_2 t)$. Having a complex probability is fine, we argue, because there is no distributed variable. At the same time, one may have a phase of 3.14 appear due to one x versus another or one t versus another or both. A phase of 3.14 corresponds to -1 and so a probability and one with the phase would cancel. This must hold in all Lorentz frames and so one requires a Lorentz invariant argument, i.e. $-Et + px$. Furthermore, this is consistent with the idea of conservation of E and p with these probabilities for x and t fixed. In fact, we show that one may consider all linear form so E, p, t, x as frame invariant and find that only $-Et + px = -m_0 c c t$ in the rest frame for $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p = mov/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0 c c / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

Next, we show that $-Et + px$ is the same as the classical action, both relativistic and nonrelativistic and that one may in fact derive $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ from Lagrangian theory. The use of a stochastic action in (1) for stochastic dynamics is consistent with what we do, but we argue that a priori, one wants a stochastic variable which is Lorentz invariant and linked with conservation, and the classical action follows from this.

Finally, we show that for a conserved stochastic variable (the classical action here), one may find probability by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint of stochastic variable * p (stochastic variable). In this case, we use a purely imaginary Lagrange multiplier.

References

1. Souza Luiz, F. et al Stochastic Dynamics from Maximum Entropy in Action Space (2026) <https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/42e46f371a5b25426c2d205a2bbc1b61425d4a26>